

DISTRIBUTION OF THE GENUS *SCUTELLARIA* L. IN THE PLANT COVER OF FERGHANA VALLEY

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Abstract. *This article presents an analysis of the results of scientific research conducted to determine the distribution of species of the genus Scutellaria of the Lamiaceae family in plant communities of Fergana Valley. To determine the distribution of species in cenotypic formations and associations of xerophilic semi-shrub plants, classical and newest publications on the local flora of Central Asia were used.*

Based on the research results, plant communities found in the cenotypes of xerophilic semi-shrub plants were identified, where species of the genus Scutellaria are common in the hills of Fergana Valley, and a list of plants Scutellaria adenostegia Briq and Scutellaria comosa Juz was compiled. Based on their wide distribution in comparison with other species in the plant communities of Adir region, new associations have been identified based on their structure.

Keywords: *formation, association, Lamiaceae, Scutellaria, cenotype, ephemeral, edificator, subedificator, assectifier, plant communities.*

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, in the context of changes occurring in the world's ecosystems as a result of the impact of biotic, abiotic and anthropogenic factors, it is necessary to determine the composition of medicinal plants in local floras, conduct a taxonomic analysis based on new approaches, create an annotated modern summary, highlight foci and study their distribution. The volume of research on the study of habitats, as well as the justification and practical use of their place in plant communities is increasing. The growth of the planet's population and the development of land areas lead to a reduction and loss of diversity of natural resources, including natural reserves of medicinal plants. In this regard, an international system for inventorying medicinal plants, the reserves of which are poorly studied and are declining as a result of external influences, has been created, and modern methods for preserving and increasing their natural resources have been developed based on an assessment of a set of factors.

Today, the important work is being carried out in our republic to identify medicinal plants, isolate new medicinal plants from them and introduce them into practice. Given the increased demand for medicinal plants from natural sources in recent years, it is necessary to assess the state of medicinal plant resources, especially to identify the species from which new medicinal plants are obtained, the natural resources and biological properties of which have not been studied. Much attention is paid to studying its place in the plant community and creating distribution maps. In the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan [1] following tasks were set: "identification of new medicinal plants, further development of the pharmaceutical industry, provision of the population and medical institutions with affordable and high-quality medicines". In implementing these tasks, the taxonomic composition and mutual relationship of species of the genus *Scutellaria* L. of the Lamiaceae family, common in Fergana Valley, were studied based on morphological features, the

distribution of species using a network mapping tool and their place in plant communities. Of great importance are studies aimed at developing recommendations for justification and conservation [15,16].

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Fergana Valley is one of the most densely populated regions not only in the republic but also in the Central Asian region, and is one of the regions most susceptible to the influence of anthropogenic factors on the environment. Since this natural-geographical region has its own unique flora and vegetation, the preservation of natural ecosystems, the determination of its floristic composition, and the restoration of harmonious relationships between man and nature are urgent tasks.

Botanical studies conducted in this area in recent years have revealed changes in the population structure of some species in the area. Some of them are influenced by anthropogenic factors, in particular, as a result of land development, overgrazing and uncontrolled logging by local people, and some species are found in unfavorable environmental conditions, such as the formation of ravines, erosion of streams and the destruction of forests. It was true for the species that it grew in rock crevices.

The studies of the flora of the valley: O.N. Bondarenko studied the flora of Namangan region, M.M. Arifkhanova - throughout Fergana Valley, R.S. Vernik and T.T. Rakhimov studied the flora of the hilly areas of Chartok, Yangikurgan, Chust and Pop districts of Namangan region, and K.Sh. Todjibaev studied the flora and meadows of Chodak River basin, and conducted research on the taxonomy, geography and economic importance of species included in a certain group in the flora of the region. Pratov conducted research on the Chenopodiaceae family, widespread in Fergana Valley, T. Khudaiberdiev - on the role of the Lamiaceae family in Fergana Valley, T.Kh. Makhkamov conducted research on the species composition of ruderal plants of Fergana Valley and their place in the vegetation cover. Floristic studies of the local flora of Fergana Valley: P.Kh. Kholkoziev conducted research on the flora of Shokhimardon reservoir in Aloy ridge, G. Gaffarov focused on the study of the flora of Khodja-Bakirgan River basin of Turkestan ridge, and N. Daminova - on the study of woody and shrubby vegetation common in Fergana Valley. In addition, in recent years, studies have been conducted to determine the species composition of groups rich in rare and endemic species, assess the scale of external impact on them, and determine the areas of their distribution. Taking this into account, a targeted study was conducted of the species composition, geography, and phytocenology of the genus *Scutellaria*, widespread in Fergana Valley, where high species diversity is observed and medicinal properties are discovered [15,16]. Until now, independent targeted studies of the species of the genus have not been conducted, which indicates the relevance of the topic.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In plant communities where species of the genus *Scutellaria* were present, the main attention was paid to the soil of the area of distribution of the species, the degree of coverage of the territory by plants, the dominant species in the plant community, ecology and floristic composition.

In the course of the study, the vegetation cover of Fergana Valley, where species of the genus are widespread, was classified on the basis of the typology adopted for plant communities by P.K. Zokirov (1989), M. Arifkhanova (1967), E.P. Korovin, R.D. Melnikova. (1971) [4, 2,6,7].

Type: Adirophytes (Adyrophyton)

Subtype: Arid steppes - Thermoxerophytes

Cenotype: Arid semi-shrubs - Xerothemithamniscia

Formation: *Artemisia sogdiana*, *Artemisia ferganensis*

The xerophilous semi-shrub senotype occupies the low hills and foothills of the entire Fergana Valley and covers the entire valley, starting from an altitude of 450 m above sea level and in places up to 1500 m [2].

Species of wormwood in the hilly regions of Fergana Valley: *Artemisia sogdiana* Bunge, *Artemisia ferganensis* Krasch. ex Poljakov, *Artemisia porrecta* Krasch. Studies have shown that *Scutellaria comosa* and *Scutellaria* ex Poljakov grow together, forming a community. M. Arifkhanova (1967) indicated *S. comosa* as part of the marigold-ephemeral-wormwood association in the foothills of Fergana Valley (Chatkal and Kurama) in the area of the villages of Chorkesar and Gowa [2]. Our studies have also shown that the species *S. comosa* is widespread in these areas. M.M. *S. comosa* was also found in other communities indicated by Arifkhanova (1967), but this species is not listed in the data provided by the scientist. This situation was more often observed in the plant communities of Aloy Ridge.

No. 17. Chatkal Ridge. Kosonsoy district, Namangan region, Almazar rural district. Kosonsoy forestry. (C 41.286321 B 71.526045). This region is a protected area, and the population of the species is not affected by external factors, including anthropogenic ones. The soil in this area is stony and rubble, and the community consists of a mixed wormwood-bellflower community. (*Scutellaria adenostegia* Briq., *S. comosa* Juz., *S. ramosissima* Popov, *Artemisia sogdiana* Bunge, *Artemisia ferganensis* Krasch. ex Polzhakov). In the community in this area, the abundance of *S. comosa* is considered an edicator of Cop1, while *S. adenostegia* Sp1, *S. ramosissima* and *S. intermedia* are very rare. Vegetation cover is 55-60%.

No. 18. Chatkal Ridge. The area around Turakurgan-Kosonsoy road in the village of Guzalabad, Turakurgan district, Namangan region (41°02'66.23" N; 71°50'77.26" E). The soil is stony and gravelly. A diverse herbaceous association of artemisinin is represented by the plant community *Artemisetum sogdiana*-mixto-fruticosum (*Artemisia sogdiana* Bunge, *Artemisia ferganensis* Krasch. ex Polzhakov, *Artemisia glaucina*, *Salvia scrophulariifolia* (Bunge) B.T.Drew, *Alcea nudiflora* (Lindl) Boiss., *Achillea biebersteinii* Afanasiev, *Agropyron repens*, *Agropyron trichophorum*, *Eremodaucus lehmannii*). Together with edicator worms, the short-tailed hawk moth participates in the first tier, there is an abundance of Sp3. The vegetation cover of the territory is about 35-40%. The plant community includes *Scutellaria comosa* Juz., *Scutellaria adenostegia* Briq. The prevalence of Sp1 was found among ascetator species. This territory is located along the highway, and in some places the species diversity is quite high. Natural disasters in the area, such as landslides caused by heavy rains and road widening, are causing the population of this species to decline.

No. 20. Kurama Ridge. Hills around Madaniyat village, Pop district, Namangan region (N 41o01'65.06"; E 70o92'19.08"). The soil in this area is stony and gravelly. Ephemeral-wormwood-blue-flowered plant community (*Scutellaria adenostegia* Briq., *S. comosa* Juz., *Artemisia sogdiana* Bunge, *Artemisia ferganensis* Krasch. ex Polzhakov, *Astragalus campylotrichus* Bunge, *Astragalus filicaulis* Kar. & Kir., *Astragalus tribuloides* Delile, *Bromus danthoniae* Trin., *Bromus tectorium* Euclidium syriacum (L.) W.T.Aiton, *Poa bulbosa* L., *Strigosella turkestanica* (Litv.) Botsch., *Strigosella Africana* (L.) Botsch., *Roemeria Refracta*

DC.) is a subdominant in the first tier, the prevalence of the edificator *Scutellaria adenostegia* in this community is Sp3, and *S. comosa* is Sp2. The second tier of ephemerals and ephemeroids included the following species: *Astragalus khartoumensis*, *Astragalus anchorifolia*, *Astragalus tenuiformis*, *Astragalus yaltyrbosh*, *Astragalus syriacus*, *Kungirbosh*, and *Chitirs* Sp1. The vegetation cover is 40-45%. Land development in this area is leading to a reduction in the species' distribution range.

No. 22. South Chatkal Range, Chartak District, Namangan Region, Mount Arbagish (N 41.267543; E 71.888002). *Artemisia sogdiana* Bunge, *Atraphaxis pyrifolia* Bunge, *Atraphaxis seravschanica* Pavlov, *Atraphaxis spinosa* L., *Salvia karelinii* J.B.Walker, *Salvia scrophulariifolia* (Bunge) B.T.Drew). The soil is rocky and gravelly. Abundance of Sogdian wormwood - Cop1, dominant, abundance of prickly pear, camel's ear, sedge and narrow-leaved khapri - Sp2-Sp3, in the grass cover there are yantok, girgensonia, hokiztili and saltwort, abundance - Sp1. , covering 35-40% of the Earth's surface. In this plant community, representatives of the genus *Scutellaria adenostegia*, *S. comosa* Sol, are very rare, that is, as assectators.

No. 25. Aloy Range. The upper part of the village of Shokhimardon is located in the basin of Shokhimardon River (N 39° 96' 53.95"; E 71° 75' 98.03"; h=1736 m). The soil in this area is rocky and gravelly. Mixed herbaceous-wormwood semi-shrub forest. (*Artemisia ferganensis* Krasch. ex Poljakov, *Artemisia glaucina*, *Salvia scrophulariifolia* (Bunge) B.T.Drew, *Salvia karelinii* J.B.Walker, *Ephedra intermedia* Schrenk & C.A. Mey., *E. equisetina*, *Zygophyllum atriplicoides* Fisch. & C.A. Mey, *Atraphaxis pyrifolia* Bunge, *Andrachne virga - tenuis* Nevsky, *Acantholimon nabievii* Lincz., *Acanthophyllum albidum* Schischk., *Capparis spinosa* L., *Scutellaria comosa* Juz., *Scutellaria oxystegia* Juz, *Salvia karelinii* J.B. Walker, *Achillea biebersteinii* Afanasiev, *Achillea filipenduliana* Lam., *Acroptilon repens* (L.) DC. *Eremurus olgae* Regel, *Salvia deserta*, *Salvia sclarea* L.). The soil is rocky and gravelly. Abundance of the edificator of Fergana wormwood Cop3, abundance of gray wormwood, mugwort and thin-leaved khapri Sp2, tuyatovona, tuyasingren, branched blueberry, Nabiev's hedgehog, white skullcap, among the blue-bellied *Scutellaria comosa*, Shrubs such as *S.oxystegia* forms the second layer with an abundance of Sp1, and the third layer contains dwarf sedges and marmaraki with an abundance of Sp1, covering 40-45% of the land surface.

No. 28. The range of Scarlet. Fergana region, Chimyon village, Fergana district, Fergana region, near a children's camp (N 40.280288; E 71.529851). Ephemeral-lingonberry-wormwood association. (*Artemisia ferganensis* Krasch. ex Polzhakov, *Artemisia scoparia* Waldst. & Kit., *Capparis spinosa* L., *Stipa caucasica*, *Roa bulbosa* L., *Botriochloa ischaemum* (L.) Keng, *Carex turkestanica* Regel). The soil in this area is stony and gravelly, brownish-gray in color. The prevalence of the edificator of Fergana wormwood in the first tier is Sp3, and the prevalence of the ephemerals of prickly sedge, Caucasian sedge, kungirbas, sedge, yaltyrbas, buzakchigir, karabas in the second tier is Sp1, covering the surface of the earth up to 30-35%. The prevalence of the representative of the genus *Scutellaria S.comosa* in this plant community is Sol, i.e. very rare.

No. 29. The range of Aloi. The hills of the village of Okbilol, Fergana district, Fergana region (N 40.299855 °; E 71.683048 °). The soil is stony and gravelly. Ephemeral wormwood (*Artemisia ferganensis* Krasch. ex Poljakov, *Artemisia diffusa* Krasch. ex Poljakov, *Bassia prostrata* (L.) Beck, *Caroxylon scleranthum* (C.A.Mey) Akani & Roalson, *Girgensohnia*

oppositiflora (Pall.) Fenzl, *Ceratocarpus arenarius* L., *Galium tricornutum* Dandy, *Stipa caucasica* Schmalh., *Roa bulbosa* L., *Botriochloa ischaemum* (L.) Keng, *Bromus danthoniae* Trin., *Carex turkestanica* Regel). The soil is stony and gravelly, gray and saline. The abundance of the edificator *Artemisia fergana* in the first tier is Sp3, the abundance of the subedificators *Izen-kokhia*, *Salsola grandiflora*, *Girgensonia* and *Ebalak saccata* in the second tier is Sp2, and the grass cover in the third tier is Three-horned Kumriot, Caucasian. The distribution of such ephemerals as *Chalovi*, *Kungirbosh*, *Chalov*, *Yaltyrbosh*, *Belaozhigir* and *Karabosh* is Sp1, covering 30-35% of the land surface. The prevalence of the representative of the genus *S. comosa* in this plant community is Sol, i.e. very rare.

No. 30. The range of Aloi. Hills of the village of Damkul, Fergana district, Fergana region (N40°31' 39.67"; E71° 80' 83.53") Blue-marsh-wormwood association (*Artemisia ferganensis* Krasch. ex Polzhakov, *Haplophyllum pedicellatum* Bunge ex Boiss., *Scutellaria comosa*). The soil is stony and gravelly, gray. The abundance of the edificator Fergana wormwood in the first tier is Sp3, tortoiseshell and cocicle blue camarona in the second tier is Sp2, and the abundance of various ephemerals in the grass cover is Sp1. The vegetation cover is 50-55%. The abundance of *S. comosa* in this area is considered a subedificator Sp2.

Artemisia ferganensis Krasch, widespread in the valley, is also present in this type, which includes *Scutellaria intermedia*, *S. ramosissima*, *S. cordifrons*, *S. adenostegia*, *S. comosa*, *S. oxystegia*, *S. chaematochlora*, *S. ocellata* and *S. urticifolia*. Examples of the former Polzhakovo Formation are ephemeral-feather-grass-wormwood, ephemeral-grass-wormwood, sedge-chachyeya-wormwood and forb-dwarf shrub-wormwood associations (Table 1). The structure of the associations is one- and two-level. Associations with various herbs include some species of shirah (*Eremurus sogdianus* (Regel) Benth. & Hook.f., *Eremurus olgae* Regel, *Eremurus regelii* Vved.), sedge, *delphinium semibarbatum* Bien. ex Boiss, beech and others.

Figure 1. *S. comosa* Tom. and *S. adenostegia* Briq. Plant communities with the participation of edificators (Akbarova, 2019)

Areas where plant communities found within the arid subshrub senotype of plants are noted:

No. 17. 17.05.2020. Chatkal Ridge. Kosonsoy District, Namangan Region, Almazar Rural District. Kosonsoy Forestry

No. 18. 18.05.2020. Chatkal Ridge. The area around the Turakurgan-Kosonsoy road in the village of Guzalabad, Turakurgan District, Namangan Region

No. 19. 24.05.2019. Kurama Ridge. Chust District, Namangan Region, the hills of the village of Ogasaroy, the right and left sides of Govasoy

No. 20. 18.05.2020. Kurama Ridge. Hills around Madaniyat village, Popsky district, Namangan region

No. 21. 05/14/2022. Kurama ridge. Chodakskoy, Papsky district, Namangan region, outskirts of Gulistan village

No. 22. 06/15/2020. Southern Chatkal ridge, Chartak district, Namangan region, Arbagish mountain

No. 23. 05/21/2020. Chatkal ridge. Yangikurgan district, Namangan region, Nanai village, Turbaza (Koksaroy) recreation area

No. 24. 06/06/2019. Aloy range. Shohimardan (Aksuv) River basin, near Yordon village

No. 25. 06/06/2019. Aloy range. Shokhimardon River Basin Upper part of Shokhimardon village

No. 26. 20.05.2022. Aloy range. The area around Demursat village, located in the Sokh River basin

No. 27. 10.05.2019. Near Imam Ota Mountain, Aloy ridge, Andijan region

No. 28. 20.05.2020. Aloy range. Fergana region, Fergana district, Chimyon village, territory of a children's camp

No. 29. 19.05.2020. Aloy range. Hills of Okbilol village, Fergana district, Fergana region

No. 30. 20.05.2020. Aloy range. Hills of Damkul village, Fergana district, Fergana region

1-table														
Species of the genus <i>Scutellaria</i> in the flora of Fergana Valley are widespread														
List of plants occurring within the <i>Xerohemithamnisca</i> senotype - Arid semi-shrub plants														
Formations	Sogdian Wormwood Formation <i>Artemisia sogdiana</i> Bunge							Fergana wormwood formation <i>Artemisia fergana</i> Krasch. former Polyakov						
	Wormwood mixed with blueberry	Various wormwoods	Mixed herbaceous semi-shrubby-wormwood forest	Ephemeral-wormwood-bluebell field	Ephemeral-ephemeral-wormwood	Khapirli-camel thorn-wormwood	Ephemeral-saltwort-wormwood	Various herbs, wormwood and mint.	Mixed herbaceous semi-shrub wormwood forest	Shirakhi-khapirli-shuyokzor	Ephemeral-chaprial-wormwood	Ephemeral-scaly-wormwood	Ephemeral sage wormwood	Blue-bellied-tussock-wormwood
Plant communities – Associations	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
<i>Atraphaxis pyrifolia</i> Bunge	-	-	-	Sol	Sol	Sol	-	-	-	Sol	Sol	-	-	-
<i>Atraphaxis seravschanica</i> Pavlov	-	-	-	Sol	Sol	-	-	-	Sol	-	Sol	-	-	-
<i>Atraphaxis spinosa</i> L.	-	-	-	Sol	Sol	-	-	-	Sol	-	Sol	-	-	-
<i>Ephedra intermedia</i> Schrenk & C. A. Mey.	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	Sol	-	-	-
<i>Ephedra equisetina</i> Bunge	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sp ₁	Sol	Sol	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	-	-	-	-
<i>Prunus spinosissima</i> Bunge Franch.	Sp ₁	-	-	Sp ₁	-	-	-	Sol	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Zygophyllum atriplicoides</i> Fisch. & C.A.Mey.	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	-	Sol	Sp ₁	-	-	Sp ₁	Sol	Sol	-	-	-
Subshrubs and shrubs														
<i>Acantholimon nabievii</i> Linez.	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	-	-	-	-	-	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	-	-	-	-
<i>Acanthophyllum albidum</i> Schischk.	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	-	-	-	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	-	Sol	Sp ₁	Sol
<i>Andrachne telephioides</i> L.	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	Sol	Sp ₁	Sol
<i>Artemisia sogdiana</i> Bunge	Sp ₃	Cop ₂	Cop ₁	Sp ₂	Cop ₃	Cop ₁	Cop ₃	Cop ₃	Sol	Sol	Sp ₁	Sol	Sol	Sol
<i>Artemisia ferganensis</i> Krasch. ex Poljakov	Sp ₂	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	Sp ₁	Cop ₁	Cop ₁	Cop ₃	Sp ₁	Sp ₃	Sp ₃

<i>Artemisia diffusa</i> Krasch. ex Poljakov	Sp1	-	-	Sp1	-	-	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	-	Sol	Sol
<i>Bassia prostrata</i> (L.) Beck	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sol	Sol	Sp1	Sol	Sp2	Sp1
<i>Krascheniukovia ceratoides</i> (L.) <i>Gueldens.</i>	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sol	Sol	Sp1	Sol	Sp1	-
<i>Salvia karelinii</i> J.B.Walker	Sol	Sol	Sol	-	-	-	-	Sp2	Sp2	Sp2	-	Sol	-	Sol
<i>Salvia scrophulariifolia</i> (Bunge) B.T.Drew	Sp1	Sp1	Sp2	Sp1	Sp1	-	-	Sp2	Sp2	Sp2	Sp1	Sol	-	Sol
<i>Salsola orientalis</i> S.G.Gmel.	Sol	Sol	Sol	-	-	-	Sp1	-	-	-	-	Sol	Sp1	Sol
<i>Scutellaria intermedia</i> Popov	Sol	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. comosa</i> Juz.	Cop3	Sp1	Sp1	Sp2	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sol	Sol	Sp1
<i>S. cordifrons</i> Juz.	-	-	-	-	-	-	Sol	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>S. ocellata</i> Juz.	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Sol	Sol	Sol	-	-
<i>S. oxystegia</i> Juz.	-	-	Sp1	-	-	-	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sol	-	-	-
<i>S. ramosissima</i> Popov	Sol	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Perennial herbs														
<i>Achillea biebersteinii</i> Afanasiev	Sp1	-	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	-	Sp1	Sol
<i>Achillea filipendulina</i> Lam.	-	Sp1	Sp1	-	-	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	-	-	Sp1	-
<i>Acroptilon repens</i> (L.) DC.	Sp1	Sp2	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	-	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sol	Sol	Sol
<i>Elymus repens</i> (L.) Gould	Sp1	-	Sp1	Sp2	Sp2	Sp1	-	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sp2	Sp1	Sol	Sol
<i>Agropyron trichophorum</i> (Link) K.Richt.	Sp1	Cop1	Cop1	Cop1	Sp1	Sp3	Cop1	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sp1	Sp1	Cop1	Sol
<i>Alcea nudiflora</i> (Lindl) Boiss.	-	-	-	Sp1	Sp1	-	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	-	-	Sol
<i>Alhagi pseudalhagi</i> (M. Bieb.) Desv. ex Wangerin	Sol	-	-	Sp2	-	-	-	Sol	Sol	Sol	-	-	-	-
<i>Botriochloa ischaemum</i> (L.) Keng	Sp1	-	-	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sol	-	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sol
<i>Capparis spinosa</i> L.	Sol	Sol	Sol	-	-	Sol	-	Sol	Sol	Sol	-	Sp1	Sol	Sol
<i>Carex turkestanica</i> Regel	Sol	-	-	Sp1	Sp1	-	Sp1	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sol

<i>Carex pachystylis</i> J.Gay	Sol	-	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sol	Sp1	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sol
<i>Centaurea squarrosa</i> Willd.	-	Sp1	-	-	Sp2	Sol	-	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sol	-	Sol
<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i> L.	Sol	Sp2	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sol	-	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sp1	Sol	-	Sol
<i>Delphinium semibarbatum</i> Bien. ex Boiss	Sol	-	-	-	Sp1	-	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sol	-	Sol	Sol	Sp1
<i>Dodartia orientalis</i> L.	-	Sp1	-	Sp1	-	-	-	Sol	Sol	Sol	-	-	-	-
<i>Eremurus olgae</i> Regel	-	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sp2	-	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp2	-	-	-
<i>Eremurus regelii</i> Vved.	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	-	-	-
<i>Eremurus sogdianus</i> (Regel) Benth.& Hook.f.	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sol	-	-	-
<i>Ferula tenuisecta</i> Korovin	-	-	Sp1	Sp3	-	-	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	-	-	-	-
<i>Haplophyllum acutifolium</i> (DC.) G. Don	-	-	Sp1	-	Sp1	-	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	-	-	Sp1
<i>Haplophyllum pedicellatum</i> Bunge ex Boiss.	-	Sp1	Sp1	-	-	-	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	-	Sol	Sol	Sp2
<i>Haplophyllum feranicum</i> Vved.	-	Sp1	Sp1	-	-	-	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sol	-	Sol	Sol	Sp1
<i>Hordeum bulbosum</i> L.	-	-	Sp2	Sp2	Sp2	Sp1	Sp1	Sol	Sol	-	Sp2	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1
<i>Peganum harmala</i> L.	Sol	Sol	Sol	-	-	-	-	Sol	-	-	-	Sol	-	-
<i>Salvia deserta</i> Schangin	-	-	-	-	Sp1	Sol	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	-	-	-
<i>Salvia sclarea</i> L.	-	-	-	Sp1	-	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	-	-	Sp1	Sol
<i>Scutellaria adenostegia</i>	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp3	Sp1	-	Sp1	-						
<i>Trichodesma incanum</i> (Bunge) A.DC.	-	Sp1	-	Sp1	Sp1	-	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	-	-	Sol
Annals, ephemerals and ephemerooids														
<i>Aegilops triuncialis</i> L.	-	Sp1	-	-	Sp1	-	-	-	-	-	Sp1	-	-	-
<i>Artemisia scoparia</i> Waldst. & Kit.	-	-	-	-	-	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sol	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sol
<i>Astragalus campylotrichus</i> Bunge	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sp2	Sp2	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sp1	Sol	Sp2	-	Sol	Sol
<i>Astragalus filicaulis</i> Kar. & Kir.	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sp1	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sp1	Sol	Sol	-	Sol	Sol
<i>Anisantha tectorum</i> (L.) Neyski	Sp1	-	-	-	Sp1	-	-	-	-	-	Sp1	-	-	-
<i>Bromus danthoniae</i> Trin.	-	-	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sp2	Sp2	-	-	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sp2	-
<i>Bromus japonicus</i> Thunb.	-	-	Sp1	Sp1	-	-	Sp1	Sol	Sol	Sol	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sol
<i>Bromus tectorum</i> L.	-	-	-	Sp1	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sol	Sol	Sol	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sol
<i>Chardinia orientalis</i> Britten	-	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sol	-	Sp1	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sp1	Sp1	Sol
<i>Ceratocarpus arenarius</i> L.	Sp2	-	-	-	-	-	Sp2	-	-	-	-	Sp1	Sp1	-

<i>Euclidium syriacum</i> (L.) W.T.Aiton	Sol	-	Sol	Sp1	Sol									
<i>Erodium cicutarium</i> (L.) L. Her	-	Sp1	-	Sp1	-	-	-	Sol	Sol	Sol	-	-	-	Sol
<i>Galium tricornerum</i> Dandy	Sol	Sol	-	Sol										
<i>Girgensohia oppositiflora</i> (Pall.) Fenzl	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	-	-	-	Sp2	-	-	-	-	Sol	Sp2	-
<i>Hordeum leporinum</i> Link	-	Sol	-	-	-	Sp1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Hypocoum parviflorum</i> Kar. & Kir.	-	-	Sol	Sp1	Sp2	-	-	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sp2	-	-	Sol
<i>Koelpinia linearis</i> Pall.	-	Sp1	-	Sp1	-	Sol	Sp1	Sol	Sol	Sol	-	Sol	Sp1	Sol
<i>Onobrychis pulchella</i> Schrenk ex Fisch. & C.A.Mey.	-	-	Sp1	-	-	-	Sp1	Sol	Sol	Sol	-	Sol	Sp1	Sol
<i>Papaver pavoninum</i> C.A.Mey.	-	Sp1	-	-	Sp1	-	-	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sp1	-	-	Sol
<i>Phleum paniculatum</i> Huds.	Sp1	-	Sol	-	-	Sol	-	Sol	Sol	Sol	-	-	-	-
<i>Poa bulbosa</i> L.	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	-	Sp1	-	Sp1	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sp1	Sp1	-	Sol
<i>Roemeria refracta</i> DC.	-	Sp2	Sol	Sp1	-	-	-	Sol	Sol	-	-	-	-	Sol
<i>Caroxylon scleranthum</i> (C.A.Mey) Akani & Roalson	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	-	-	-	Sp1	-	-	-	-	Sol	Sp1	-
<i>Strigosella Africana</i> (L.) Botsch.	-	-	Sol	Sp1	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sol	-	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sol
<i>Strigosella turkestanica</i> (Lity.) Botsch.	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sp1	Sol	Sol	Sol	-	-	-	Sol	Sol	Sol	-
<i>Thaenatherum crinitum</i> (Schreb.) Neyski	-	Sp3	-	Sp1	-	-	-	Sol	-	-	-	-	Sol	-
<i>Trigonella grandiflora</i> Bunge	-	Sp1	Sp2	-	-	Sol	-	-	-	-	Sp2	-	Sp2	-
<i>Turgenia latifolia</i> (L.) Hoffm.	Sol	-	-	-	Sp2	Sol	Sp2	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sp2	Sol	Sp2	Sol
<i>Vicia angustifolia</i> L.	-	-	-	Sol	Sol	-	Sp2	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sol	Sp2	Sol
<i>Ziziphora tenuior</i> L.	Sp1	-	-	Sp1	Sp1	-	-	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sp1	Sol	-	Sp1

CONCLUSION

Until now, no targeted studies on the study of species of the genus *Scutellaria* have been conducted in Uzbekistan. In this context, the conducted research, the critical approach based on the available sources and the formation of new knowledge about the taxonomic diversity, biogeography and distribution of species of the genus *Scutellaria* in plant communities have important scientific and practical significance. The practical significance of the research results lies in the fact that the prepared GAT maps and the cadastre of species of the genus *Scutellaria* will serve as a basis for developing an action plan for the protection of species of this genus in the vegetation cover of Namangan and Fergana regions, as well as for organizing future monitoring of populations of rare and endangered species.

It has been established that in the lower part of the valley, in Chust, Pop, Chortok, Chimyon, Damkul, Sokh and other areas, the habitat of species of the genus is currently shrinking, and the composition of these plant communities is changing.

The arid semi-shrub plant senotype of Fergana Valley is characterized by semi-shrub or thorny areas of the foothills, lower parts of the mountains and the hilly zone, which is considered arid (xerophilic) by its nature, with direct contact with communities of wormwood, ephemerals and broad-leaved trees limited and together with them form certain plant communities. The soils of the areas of distribution of these plant communities are represented mainly by sierozems, and in most cases, these phytocenoses are found on dry, gravelly soils. In these areas, more precipitation falls in deserts, so these plants ensure the stability of phytocenoses. These are mainly representatives of the *Artemisia* family, edificators of this type, as well as several wormwoods: *Artemisia sogdiana*, *A. tenuisecta*, *A. serotina*, *A. ferganensis*, *A. glanduligera*, *A. lehmanniana*, *A. leucodes*, *A. porrecta* and sage *Salvia scrophulariifolia* is considered. This type of xerophilous subshrub plants mainly includes two groups: wormwoods and subshrub and subshrub groups of plants of the *Lamiaceae* family.

From the wormwoods, the most widespread is *Artemisia ferganensis*, which forms several associations throughout the Central Fergana Plain and in the hilly parts of the valley. The next most widespread association is *Artemisia sogdiana*, distributed along the foothills and partly along the lower slopes of Kuramin and Chatkal ranges. Third place is occupied by *Artemisia glaucium*, which participates as an edificator of oil plant communities. Other species of wormwood do not play such an important role in the formation of valley landscapes.

We can show associations of the *Artemisia ferganensis* formation, widespread in the valley. On the sierozems of the hilly zone, the Sogdian wormwood formation grows - *Artemisia sogdiana*. Depending on the habitat, they are common on stony, gravelly and sandy soils, forming associations with shrubs, sedges, various herbs, ephemerals and ephemeroïds.

In Namangan Mountains, the following shrubs are characteristic of these associations: *Zygorhyllum atriplicoides*, *Z. ferganense*, *Atraphaxis seravschanica*. Wormwood forests with *Salvia scrophulariifolia* are widespread in Chust-Pop Mountains, where these areas are found along old, dry streams with gravel.

The associations belonging to this type include: *Euclidium syriacum*, *Astragalus campylorhynchus*, *A. filicaulis*, *A. tribuloides*, *Malcolmia turkestanica*, *M. africana*, *M. trichocarpa*, *Arenaria serpillifolia*, *Roemeria reflecta*, *Papaver pavoninum*, *Bromus danthoniae*, *B. oxyodon*, *B. japonicus*, *B. tectorum* and *Ziziphora tenuior* with plants of the genus *Scutellaria*:

Scutellaria intermedia, S. ramosissima, S. cordifrons, S. adenostegia, S. comosa, S. oxystegia, S. ocellata, S. chaematochlora, S. urticifolia. Other species were also found to be involved.

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